

A checklist of the threatened spider species in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: The emerging field of conservation biogeography examines species' distribution dynamics and their relationship to biodiversity conservation. In South Africa, from 2016 to 2019, a total of 2 265 species from 76 069 records were used for the first time in a conservation assessment. The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species Categories and Criteria, which reflect a species' extinction risk, were used. Only South African species were assessed; Eswatini and Lesotho were excluded. Of the assessed taxa, most species (1 445, 63%) are widely distributed and have no known threats, while 691 species (31%) have insufficient information to make a direct or indirect assessment. Only 60 species (2.6%) were assessed as IUCN Threatened Species: four species (0.1%) are classified as Critically Endangered (CR), 23 species (1.1%) as Endangered (EN), and 33 species (1.4%) as Vulnerable (VU). The South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) uses additional categories for South African taxa to highlight species that they are not necessarily threatened but are of high conservation concern due to extreme rarity and 69 species (3%) were listed as such.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation, red listing, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The emerging field of conservation biogeography concerns species' distribution dynamics and their relationship to biodiversity conservation (Robertson *et al.*, 2010). The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), initiated in 1997 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), has the primary aim of documenting the arachnid fauna of South Africa. Distribution records for all known South African species were extracted from original descriptions, redescriptions, and revisionary work, as well as from species newly recorded during ecological surveys (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010). This resulted in a complete data set as it also included species housed in overseas museum collections. As part of SANSa, all this data was collated in a relational database maintained by the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Descriptions of South African spider species experienced two periods of rapid growth, the first at the start of the previous century and the second, which corresponds with the initiation of SANSa in 1997 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). SANSa has resulted in a 33% increase in newly recorded and described spider species. The number of accessions in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection (Figs 1 & 2) increased by 350% since the initiation of SANSa phase II in 2006, when funding became available from the Threatened Species Program at the South African Biodiversity Institute (SANBI).

In South Africa from 2016 to 2019, spiders were assessed for the first time using the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species Categories and Criteria, which reflect a species' extinction risk. In the latest checklist 2 265 species are listed from South Africa with their conservation assessment (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Of the assessed taxa, only 78 species (4%) were assessed as threatened and a checklist of these species of special concern is provided here.

METHODS

The spider species assessed for the first time using the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species categories and criteria only dealt with South African species, Eswatini and Lesotho species were excluded (Foord *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). Records in the SANSa database that were not identified up to species level were excluded from the data used for Red List assessments. A total of 23 827 records were therefore used and the distribution of occurrence of species across South Africa was visualised using quarter-degree, degree-square, and density-kernel plots for all records (76 069).

Analysis for Red List assessments was performed using the red data set (Cardoso, 2017). Spatial analysis on observed occurrences using functions for Extent of Occurrence (EOO), Area of Occupancy (AOO), and elevational range was used. The assumed knowledge of the full range for all species based on their observed occurrences, and EOO was calculated as the minimum convex polygon around all occurrences, and the 2 km² cells occupied were used to calculate AOO (Foord *et al.*, 2020). EOOs smaller than the AOO were made equal. The distribution of threats across lineages was visualised using a mosaic plot, with the size of rectangles representing the proportion of species in a specific family represented within three categories: data deficient, least concern, and of special concern

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Figures 1-2. 1. The National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the ARC-Plant Health and Protection at Roodeplaat. 2. The National Arachnida collection.

IUCN RED LIST CATEGORIES AND CRITERIA

The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) uses a standardized system called the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria to classify species according to their risk of extinction. This system was used to do conservation assessments of South African spiders (Table 2). There are nine official categories used in IUCN conservation assessments:

1. **Not Evaluated (NE):** Species that have not yet been assessed against the IUCN criteria.
2. **Data Deficient (DD):** There is inadequate information to make a direct or indirect assessment of extinction risk.
3. **Least Concern (LC):** Species are widespread and abundant; they do not meet the criteria for a threatened category.
4. **Near Threatened (NT):** Species are close to qualifying for a threatened category or likely to qualify soon.
5. **Vulnerable (VU):** Species face a high risk of extinction in the wild.
6. **Endangered (EN):** Species face a very high risk of extinction in the wild.
7. **Critically Endangered (CR):** Species face an extremely high risk of extinction in the wild.
8. **Extinct in the Wild (EW):** Species survive only in captivity, cultivation, or as a naturalized population outside its historical range.
9. **Extinct (EX):** No reasonable doubt exist that the last individual of the species has died.

SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL BIODIVERSITY INSTITUTE CATEGORIES

The South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) use The categories Rare (R) and Critically Rare (CR) although they do not form part of the IUCN system (Table 3). These categories are used to flag species of exceptionally high conservation concern, even when they are not yet declining. They explicitly used it to ensure that naturally range-restricted endemic species are not overlooked in land-use planning, EIAs, or development decisions.

Rare: A species may be listed as Rare if it meets any one of the following:

Restricted range: Extent of Occurrence (EOO) < 500 km²

Habitat specialist: Area of Occupancy (AOO) < 20 km²

Low population density: Occurs as single individuals or small subpopulations (often < 50 mature individuals per subpopulation)

Small global population: Fewer than 10 000 mature individuals worldwide

Critically Rare: A species that is extremely range-restricted or confined to a single site, with very few known populations, and where any additional disturbance could immediately drive it towards extinction, even if there is no current decline. This category is used mainly for plants and some invertebrates. In spider and invertebrate assessments, Critically Rare is often applied when: a species is known from one cave, forest patch, mountain slope, or dune system; there may, as yet, be no evidence of decline, but any habitat loss would be catastrophic.

SOUTH AFRICAN SPIDER SPECIES LISTED AT THE IUCN

South Africa has one of the most comprehensive spider conservation assessments in the world and many species have IUCN-style conservation statuses. Only a small number are currently listed individually on the global IUCN website. The IUCN Red List system classifies how endangered a species is using different categories.

RESULTS

Family diversity: In a checklist published by Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. (2023), 2 265 spider species and subspecies, 495 genera and 71 families were listed. Of the 71 spider families known from South Africa, the Salticidae (jumping spiders) is the most species rich (354 species), followed by the Gnaphosidae (195 species) and Thomisidae (143 species).

Endemicity: Most species (1 419 species, 63%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern. There are 675 spider species (30%) classified as Data Deficient, underscoring the need for further research to better understand them and assess their threat status. Data-deficient species are usually known from only one sex or based on old material without detailed locality data, or where the species are not recently redescribed or illustrated. Many species recorded from South Africa (946 species, 41.4%) are still only known from one sex and 23 species were described from juveniles, resulting in the high number of Data Deficient species.

Species of special concern: Only 60 species (2.6%) were assessed as threatened IUCN species: four species (0.1%) are classified as Critically Endangered (CR), 23 species (1.1%) as Endangered (EN), 33 species (1.4%) are Vulnerable (VU) and 4 species (0.2%) are Near Threatened (NT). The SANBI category flagged 62 species of high conservation concern due to extreme rarity. No spider species is extinct or possibly extinct.

However, it is the smaller, more delicate spiders frequently found in darker, hidden habitats, such as caves, that are of greatest concern. This includes families such as Archaeidae (6 species), Pholcidae (20 species) and some Zodariidae (9 species).

Several of the larger Mygalomorphae ground dwellers are also of special concern but that is mainly because they are not easily seen or collected. This group include: Entypesidae (1 species), Idiopidae (5 species), Microstigmatidae (1 species), Migidae (5 species), Pycnothelidae (1 species), Stasimopidae (4) and Theraphosidae (3) (Table 1 & 2).

TO SUMMARIZE

Threatened species (IUCN) (60 spp.):

- 4 species Critically Endangered (CR)
- 23 species (1.1%) as Endangered (EN)
- 33 species 1.4% as Vulnerable (VU)
- 4 species (0.2%) as Near Threatened (NT)

Rarity categories (SANBI) (62 spp.):

- 17 species (0.8%) were listed as Critically Rare
- 45 species (1.9%) as Rare

More information:

- 1 445 species (63%) are widely distributed with no known threats and are of Least Concern
- 691 species (31%) are data deficient
- Endemism is high, and 1303 species (59%) are only found in South Africa, 2.4% of the World’s fauna
- 946 species, 41.4%) are known only from one sex
- 23 species were described from juveniles

Main threats to spiders: Biodiversity inventories are essential to identify key areas for conservation and to monitor the effects of threats. Research on spider ecology in South Africa focused on local-scale studies on how spider assemblage responses to habitat complexity, landscape scale variables, ecosystem rehabilitation and plant invasions, and disturbance effects such as fire, grazing and chemical control. Spiders face a variety of natural and human-related threats, of which the main threats are:

• PREDATORS

Spiders are a normal part of the food chain and help to keep prey populations balanced in controlling pests in agro-ecosystems (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013). But many animals hunt spiders for food. This includes animals, such as birds (Kopij, 2000; Jones, 2011), small mammals (Kerley, 1989), monkeys (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2011); reptiles and amphibians such as lizards, frogs and toads (Nagy *et al.*, 1984); insects like wasps and assassin bugs (Gess & Gess, 1980; Nel *et al.*, 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025).

• NATURAL THREATS

Natural disasters such as floods, fires, droughts, and storms can destroy spider habitats, kill spiders, and reduce their food supply, forcing them to move or causing populations to decline. Floods, for example, can destroy burrows and webs, while fires can burn vegetation and directly kill spiders. Studies in South Africa looked at the effect of fire on spiders (Lubin & Crouch, 2003; Uys *et al.*, 2006; Pryke & Samways, 2012; Haddad *et al.*, 2015).

• ENVIRONMENTAL CHANGES

Changes in temperature, humidity, or seasons can affect their survival. Extreme weather events can destroy webs and habitats. Currently climate change is making these effects worse, and some studies focus on determining the possible effects (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2016).

• HUMAN-RELATED THREATS

Habitat loss is one of the biggest threats. This includes removing places where spiders live and hunt such as deforestation; urban development and farming expansion. Studies examined overgrazing of cattle (Seymour & Dean, 1999; Jansen *et al.*, 2013), sheep farming (Henschel & Lubin, 2018) as well elephant-induced habitat changes (Haddad *et al.*, 2010); effect of long-term mammal herbivory (Ukwevho *et al.*, 2023); effect of Bt-cotton cultivation (Mellet *et al.*, 2006); land use changes (Foord *et al.*, 2018; Joseph *et al.*, 2017; Yekwayo *et al.*, 2017) and mining in coastal dune forest (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wassenaar, 2002, 2006).

• PESTICIDES AND POLLUTION

Chemicals like heavy metals or microplastics affect the ability to produce effective webs. They also reduce reproduction and may reduce spider diversity and abundance and feeding behaviour (Virbhan, 2025). Pesticides and herbicides are among the most detrimental pollutants affecting spider populations in agriculture. Insecticides not only reduce prey availability but also have direct toxic effects on spiders. Research looked at the effect of cover spraying in the control of termites on spiders (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1978) and the control of pest species in cotton (Van den Berg *et al.*, 1990). Soil pollution, primarily caused by agricultural runoff, industrial waste, urbanization and heavy metal accumulation, can affect burrowing and ground-dwelling spiders, while semi-aquatic spiders are particularly vulnerable to freshwater and seashore contamination, which can lead to bioaccumulation of toxins.

Artificial light at night significantly affects nocturnal spiders by disrupting their natural behaviours. Many spider species rely on darkness for hunting, mating, and web construction. Increased exposure to artificial lighting can alter circadian rhythms, reduce predation efficiency, and influence web placement.

• INVASIVE SPECIES

Non-native animals or plants can disrupt ecosystems where spiders live. Research in South Africa looked at the effect of invasive weeds such as *Chromolaena odorata* (Mgobozi *et al.*, 2008) and *Opuntia stricta* (Robertson *et al.*, 2011) on spider populations.

TABLE 1. The spider families with the number of species that are currently regard as being of special concern.

FAMILY	SPP.	FAMILY	SPP.
Anapidae	1	Penestomidae	2
Araneidae	3	Pholcidae	20
Archaeidae	6	Phyxelididae	4
Atypidae	2	Pycnothelidae	1
Caponiidae	2	Salticidae	11
Cheiracanthiidae	1	Scytodidae	2
Corinnidae	5	Selenopidae	1
Cyatholipidae	4	Sicariidae	1
Drymusidae	4	Sparassidae	3
Entypesidae	1	Stasimopidae	4
Gallieniellidae	3	Telemidae	1
Hersiliidae	1	Tetragnathidae	1
Idiopidae	5	Theraphosidae	3
Linyphiidae	2	Thomisidae	3
Lycosidae	1	Trachelidae	4
Macrobunidae	2	Zodariidae	9
Microstigmatidae	1	Zoropsidae	3
Migidae	5		

Amaurobioides africana a semi-aquatic spider that is vulnerable for seashore contamination. Credit: Charles Haddad.

TABLE 2. South African spider species off special concern based in the IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria.

CRITICALLY ENDANGERED (CR)

Afrarchaea fernkloofensis Lotz, 1996
Afrarchaea entabeniensis Lotz, 2003
Caerostris tinamaze Gregorič, 2015
Diploglena proxila Haddad, 2015

ENDANGERED (EN)

Afrarchaea woodae Lotz, 2006
Cladomelea akermani Hewitt, 1923
Cladomelea debeeri Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004
Diploglena dippenaarae Haddad, 2015
Drassodella tenebrosa Lawrence, 1938
Galeosoma hirsutum Hewitt, 1916
Galeosoma pallidum Hewitt, 1915
Galeosoma scutatatum Purcell, 1903
Griswoldia zuluensis (Lawrence, 1938)
Heliophanus africanus Wesolowska, 1986
Homalattus punctatus Peckham & Peckham, 1903
Icius nigricaudus Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009
Moggridgea loistata Griswold, 1987
Moggridgea quercina Simon, 1903
Palystes kreutzmanni Jäger & Kunz, 2010
Procydrela procursor Jocqué, 1999
Quamtana knysna Huber, 2003
Rotundrela rotunda Jocqué, 1999
Smeringopus dehoop Huber, 2012
Stasimopus filmeri Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012
Stasimopus griswoldi Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012
Thyenula clarisognata Wesolowska et al., 2014
Thyenula rufa Wesolowska et al., 2014

VULNERABLE (VU)

Afrarchaea cornutus Lotz, 2003
Afrarchaea ngomensis Lotz, 1996
Austrachelas incertus Lawrence, 1938
Brachytheliscus bicolor Pocock, 1897
Calommata transvaalica Hewitt, 1916
Ceratogyrus paulseni Gallon, 2005
Diores dowsetti Jocqué, 1990
Erigonops littoralis (Hewitt, 1915)
Euophrys bifida Wesolowska et al., 2014
Fuchibotulus bicornis Haddad & Lyle, 2008
Galeosoma robertsi Hewitt, 1916
Griswoldia melana (Lawrence, 1938)
Hortipes atalante Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000
Hortipes coccinatus Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000
Hortipes merwei Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000
Idiops pretoriae (Pocock, 1898)

VULNERABLE (cont.)

Ilisoa knysna Griswold, 1987
Isicabu zuluensis Griswold, 1987
Loxosceles speluncarum Simon, 1893
Massagris natalensis Wesolowska & Haddad, 2009
Moggridgea terricola Simon, 1903
Mystaria lindaicapensis Lewis & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014
Pionothele straminea Purcell, 1902
Psammoduon arenicola (Simon, 1910)
Quamtana embuleni Huber, 2003
Quamtana lajuma Huber, 2003
Scytodes gooldi Purcell, 1904
Spinotrachelas montanus Haddad et al., 2011
Stasimopus hewitti Engelbrecht & Prendini, 2012
Themacrys silvicola (Lawrence, 1938)
Tyrotama soutpansbergensis Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2005
Vidole helicityna Griswold, 1990
Xevioso lichmadina Griswold, 1990

NEAR THREATENED (NT)

Calommata meridionalis Fourie et al., 2011
Griswoldia punctata (Lawrence, 1942)
Panaretella distincta (Pocock, 1896)
Simorcus haddadi Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2010

Tyrotama soutpansbergensis female, a Vulnerable species. Credit: Peter Webb

Mystaria lindaicapensis female, a Vulnerable species. Credit: Linda Wiese.

TABLE 3. Spider species flagged based on the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) categories of Rare (R) and Critically Rare (CR).

CRITICALLY RARE

Cangoderces lewisi Harington, 1951
Cheiramiona hogsbackensis Lotz, 2015
Crozetulus scutatus (Lawrence, 1964)
Heriaeus muizenberg Van Niekerk & D-Schoeman, 2013
Lepthyphantes rimicola Lawrence, 1964
Pterartoria cederbergensis Russell-Smith & Roberts, 2017
Quamtana leptopholcica (Strand, 1909)
Quamtana mbaba Huber, 2003
Quamtana merwei Huber, 2003
Quamtana meyeri Huber, 2003
Quamtana nandi Huber, 2003
Quamtana umzinto Huber, 2003
Quamtana nylsvley Huber, 2003
Smeringopus blyde Huber, 2012
Smeringopus lydenberg Hubert, 2012
Spermophora schoemanae Huber, 2003
Stasimopus mandelai Hendrixson & Bond, 2004

RARE

Afrarchaea neethlingi Lotz, 2017
Afroseto capensis Lyle & Haddad, 2010
Afrodrassex catharinae Haddad & Booysen, 2022
Anyphops kraussi (Pocock, 1898)
Austrachelas wassenaari Haddad *et al.*, 2009
Australutica africana Jocqué, 2008
Chinophrys trifasciata Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Chumma striata Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2017
Cyatholipus tortilis Griswold, 1987
Diores leleupi Jocqué, 1990
Diores setosus Tucker, 1920
Diores silvestris Jocqué, 1990
Diphya wesolowskiae Omelko *et al.*, 2020
Hortipes contubernalis Bossler's & Jocqué, 2000
Jocquestus incurvus Lyle & Haddad, 2018
Idiothele mira Gallon, 2010
Ilisoa conjugalis Griswold, 2001
Izithunzi capense (Simon, 1893)
Izithunzi lina Labarque *et al.*, 2017
Izithunzi productum (Purcell, 1904)
Izithunzi silvicola (Purcell, 1904)
Malaika longipes (Purcell, 1904)
Microstigmata amatola Griswold, 1985
Moggridgea intermedia Hewitt, 1913
Moggridgea teresae Griswold, 1987
Palystes martinfilmeri Croeser, 1996
Penestomus egazini Miller *et al.*, 2010

Penestomus montanus Miller *et al.*, 2010
Phanotea ceratogyna Griswold, 1994
Phanotea peringueyi Simon, 1896
Pterartoria cederbergensis Russell-Smith & Roberts, 2017
Pterinochilus lapalala Gallon & Engelbrecht, 2011
Quamtana ciliata (Lawrence, 1938)
Quamtana embuleni Huber, 2003
Quamtana entabeni Huber, 2003
Rotundrela orbiculata Jocqué, 1999
Rumburak lateripunctatus Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Rumburak mirabilis Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Tanzania striatus Wesolowska *et al.*, 2014
Scytodes montana Purcell, 1904
Smeringopus hanglip Huber, 2012
Smeringopus mlilwane Huber, 2012
Smeringopus ndumo Huber, 2012
Spermophora gordimeriae Huber, 2003
Spermophora peninsulae Lawrence, 1964

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As found for so many other taxa, South Africa has a remarkable diversity of spiders. The majority of species are of least concern and only a small percentage are threatened. Threats are linked to a variety of environmental changes many linked to agriculture and urbanization. However the importance of temperature and climate change in future will become more important. It is very important to monitor the population of species that are of special concern, as well as the large number of species that lack data and could not be assessed. Here the citizen scientist and platforms like iNaturalist might play an important role.

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An updated review of the polymorphic crab spider *Thomisus citrinellus* Simon, 1875

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ABSTRACT: *Thomisus spinifer* O. Pickard-Cambridge (1872) was described from specimens from Jordan. However, the name *T. spinifer* was preoccupied, rendering it invalid. *Thomisus citrinellus*, described by Simon (1875) based on a female specimen from the southern side of the Pyrenees, between France and Spain, became the accepted name to replace *T. spinifer*. But the nomenclatural history of the species is complex, involving multiple synonyms. In the description of *T. citrinellus*, an irregular triangular marking and short transverse bands on the abdomen are distinctive for the species, and the legs have bands and spots. These markings correspond with observations of the species by different authors throughout Africa. With more than 100 photographs available of live spiders, at least two colour morphs in shades of pink or brown are seen.

Keywords: biodiversity, colour change, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Thomisus spinifer O. Pickard-Cambridge (1872) was described from a specimen collected from Jordan. However, the name *T. spinifer* was already preoccupied, rendering it invalid according to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN). The species *Thomisus citrinellus*, described by Simon (1875), has become the accepted name to replace *T. spinifer* (Roewer, 1955) and is listed as such in the World Spider Catalog (2026), with verified taxonomic standing in the Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS). However, its nomenclatural history is complex, involving multiple synonyms. *Thomisus citrinellus* was described from a female sampled from “Pyrénées espagnoles” an area on the southern side of the Pyrenees mountain range between France and Spain. The World Spider Catalog (2026) listed *T. citrinellus* as widely distributed across Spain, France, Cyprus, Turkey, Africa, Seychelles, Yemen (incl. Socotra), Israel, and Iraq and possibly Iran. In this paper the presence of *T. citrinellus* in Africa is reviewed with notes on the different colour morphs found.

METHODS

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), many *T. citrinellus* specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled, and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). As part of the SANSA Virtual Museum photograph database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) numerous images were received that provided additional information on the species. Images of the species was also sourced from iNaturalist, a global community science platform.

RESULTS

***Thomisus spinifer* records from Africa:** Publications indicate that *T. citrinellus* has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa, Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983) revised the *Thomisus* species of southern Africa, and examined numerous specimens from Africa housed in several museums abroad. *Thomisus citrinellus* are presently reported from: Algeria (Beladjal *et al.*, 2025); Botswana (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Kassimatis, 2002); Chad (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); Egypt (Sallam, 2012); Djibouti (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1989); Ethiopia (Caporiacco, 1941; Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); French Guinea (Millot, 1942); Kenya (Caporiacco, 1949; Kioko *et al.*, 2021); Mali (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983); Mozambique (Lessert, 1936); Namibia (NCA); Senegal (Simon, 1886; Caporiacco, 1941); South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023); Tanzania (Russell-Smith, 2020); Uganda (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983) and Zimbabwe (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1983).

Figures 1–2. *Thomisus citrinellus*. 1. Female from Heidelberg in Gauteng. 2. Male from Hoedspruit. Credits: 1. Johan van Zyl. 2. Peter Webb.

Figure 3–7. *Thomisus citrinellus*. 3. Female habitus from French Guinea. 4. Epigyne. 5. Female habitus from South Africa. 6. Epigyne. 7. *Thomisus citrinellus* female, first record from eSwatini. Credits: 3–4. After Millot (1942). 5–6. After Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983). 7. Phil White.

Female diagnostic characters: Simon (1875) described the holotype female, noting abdominal markings consisting of an irregular triangular dark mark followed by short transverse bands, and mentions the bands and spots on the legs. This corresponds to the markings shown in Fig. 1. Only in 1886 did Simon mention the darker mediolateral bands on the carapace of a female from Senegal. In the same paper, he provided the first drawing of the male palp (Fig. 15). Both Lessert (1936), with specimens from Mozambique, and Caporiacco (1941), with specimens from Senegal and Ethiopia, observed the dark mediolateral bands on the carapace, the bands on the anterior legs, and the markings on the abdomen. Millot (1942) provided the first illustrations of a female from French Guinea (Figs 4 & 5). He clearly illustrated the abdominal markings as described by Simon (1875). But due to the complex nomenclatural history, the invalidity of *T. spinifer*, the subspecies *T. spinifer decorata* (Millot, 1942); *T. spinifer simoni*, *T. spinifer obscurus* and *T. spinifer maculata* Caporiacco (1941; 1949) were regarded as synonyms of *T. citrinellus* by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983).

Colour morphs: In museum specimens or alcohol-collected individuals, pink pigments may degrade post-mortem, appearing fawn to brown (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025b). This is especially relevant when comparing live vs preserved colouration. With more than 100 images of live *T. citrinellus* available, two colour morphs have been recognised.

A few specimens are fawn with brown markings (Figs 15–17), while the majority are white with pink markings (Figs 1, 8–14). The pink colouration in *T. citrinellus* is primarily due to stable, lipochrome pigments in the hypodermis, rather than reversible pigment dynamics like those seen in yellow-white transitions of other *Thomisus* species (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a). The pink colour is more persistent and not withdrawn or redistributed like ommochromes (yellow pigments). The cuticle and hypodermis are partially transparent, allowing pink pigments to interact with underlying guanine crystals. These markings are not known to change with background, supporting their role as fixed traits (Gawryszewski *et al.*, 2015; Herberstein & Gawryszewski, 2012). Lipochromes that accumulate in hypodermal cells form the characteristic markings as described by Simon (1875; 1886). This pink colouration tends to intensify with age (Fig. 14), suggesting a developmental trajectory rather than an environmentally induced change. Brown colouration sometimes replaces pink in *T. citrinellus*. It could be melanin accumulation that overrides lighter pigments, turning pink to brown or ommochrome degradation that may also result in brownish tones replacing pink.

If pink is derived from unstable pigments (e.g. ommochromes or carotenoids), it may fade or oxidise into brown under certain conditions. Brown may be favoured in habitats with leaf litter, grasses, and bark, which offer better camouflage (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a).

Figure 8–14. Examples of pink morphs showing the different variations of the basic markings. Credits: 8. Peter Webb. 9. Sally Adam. 10. Lynette Rudmann. 11. Les Oates. 12. Cecile Roux. 13. Andrea Sander. 14. S. Boyd.

Figure 15–17. Examples of brown morphs showing the different variations of the basic markings. Credits: 15. Linda Wiese. 16. Vida van der Walt. 17. Andrea Sander.

Figure 15–18. *Thomisus citrinellus* male. 15. Male palp drawing after Simon (1886) from Senegal. 16. Male habitus after Millot (1942). 17. Male palp after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1989). 18. Male (Ian Anderson).

Male: The male is much smaller than the female. Simon (1886) provided the first drawing of the male palp (Fig. 15), which corresponds to that of Dippenaar-Schoeman (1983; 1989) (Fig. 17). The palp is very distinctive as it bears two slightly curved retrolateral apophyses on the palpal tibia and a large downward-inclined tegulum. In the male (Figs 1, 16 & 18), the carapace is brown and covered with long erect setae. Legs with front legs brown, tibiae I and II darker brown with metatarsi with a faint darker band that varies between specimens; posterior legs pale brown. The abdomen is covered with numerous erect setae. However, the bodies of males of several species resemble each other; sometimes, only bands on the front legs vary. But the leg bands also vary between specimens, and the only way to identify the species is to examine the male palp. Also, assuming that males found on females' abdomens are the same species as the females is not always correct, as they are frequently killed by females.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Thomisus citrinellus is a common species and is currently known from 19 African countries. The female is recognised by the mediolateral bands on the carapace and, on the abdomen, an irregular triangular marking followed by short, wavy posterior bands. The abdomen sometimes has a round, dark spot on each tubercle. In the male several species resemble each other; sometimes, only differing by the bands on the front legs. But the leg bands also vary between specimens, and the only way to identify the species correctly is to examine the male palp. Also, males found on females' abdomens are not always of the same species, and they are then killed (Fig. 21).

With the large number of images available, two colour morphs, pink or brown, have been identified. However most specimens are pink, and the darker body markings are present in all, but do vary in shape (Figs 7-14). *Thomisus citrinellus* seems not to change colour as observed in some other *Thomisus* species.

This was also observed by Levy (1973), who reported that the species is unable to change colour. However, we observed some variations in body patterns. In Fig. 19, the colouration is dark and possibly melanin based. Melanistic morphs in Thomisidae are possibly underreported due to seasonal, sexual, or ontogenetic variation (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2025a) but have been observed in several thomisid genera. In Fig. 20, the female has all the pink markings but with a yellow undertone.

With further research and more information now available, *Thomisus ghesquierei* Lessert, 1943, as reported on by Dippenaar-Schoeman (2023), might in reality be the brown morph of *T. citrinellus*. However, specimens are needed to study genitalia for confirmation.

Figure 19. *Thomisus citrinellus* female dark variation (Heather and Andrew Hodgson)

Figure 20. *Thomisus citrinellus* female with yellow tint (Vida vd Walt)

Figure 21. *Thomisus citrinellus* female feeding on a male that is not conspecific.

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First records of *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930 from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930, was described from the Democratic Republic of Congo based on a single female. Here we report on a female from South Africa for the first time. The general morphology and distribution of the species is discussed with notes on its lifestyle. The male is still unknown.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida.

INTRODUCTION

Aethriscus Pocock, 1902 is a rare African genus of orb-weaver spider family Araneidae known only from two African species (World Spider Catalog, 2026). It is listed in the subfamily Cyrtarachninae in the Cyrtarachnini. Cyrtarachninae is a subfamily that is notable for its highly specialized predatory strategies, especially moth specialization, unusual web architectures, such as spanning-thread webs, triangular webs, and bolas, while some are webless with effective using masquerade and chemical deception (Stowe, 1986; Tanikawa *et al.*, 2014). The group was first established by Simon (1892), originally as Cyrtarachneae, and has since been treated at different taxonomic ranks (Sharff & Coddington 2020; *et al.*, 2014).

Little is known about the behaviour of the *Aethriscus* species, only that they are known as bird-dropping spiders. They rely on extreme crypsis and immobility when resting, resembling bird droppings. This is supported by their shiny bodies and short legs that fold around the body (Figs 1 & 4). When a spider is seen but misidentified as uninteresting by predators, it is a form of defensive mimicry called masquerade. Masquerade is a special type of protective mimicry where an organism avoids being eaten by resembling an inanimate object that predators normally ignore, such as a twig, leaf, stone, or bird dropping. The key idea is misidentification: the predator sees the organism but mistakenly identifies it as something that is not food. This enables the spiders to rest unnoticed during the day in exposed places on the upper surface of leaves.

Although *Aethriscus* is recorded from two African countries, very few specimens have been collected, and few field observations have been made. *Aethriscus olivaceus* Pocock, 1902 and *A. pani* Lessert, 1930, are known only from females, and both were described from the Democratic Republic of Congo and re-collected from South Africa. *Aethriscus olivaceus* was first reported from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022), and in this paper, we provide the first records of *A. pani* from South Africa.

METHODS

A female *A. pani* was collected in 2026 in Gauteng and the specimen was kept alive in a large terrarium. She died and a voucher specimen is deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Institute in Pretoria. Data sourced from iNaturalist, a global community science platform, resulted in only one additional record (Fig. 4) from the Limpopo province.

TAXONOMY

Diagnostic characters: *Aethriscus pani* Lessert, 1930 was described from Democratic Republic of Congo. Female total length 10 mm. Carapace is fawn, smooth and shiny with blackish hue; with small tubercles present at the cephalic region constriction; the carapace is wider than long with sides rounded, narrowed in eye region (Fig. 3). Eyes in two rows (Fig. 5) with the median and lateral eyes on tubercles (Figs 5 & 9) and the median eyes closely group, three times closer to each other than the laterals; anterior eyes slightly larger than posterior eyes.

Figure 1–3. *Aethriscus pani* female from Gauteng. 1. Anterior view. 2. Ventral view. 3. Dorsal view. Credit: John Leroy.

Figure 4–5. *Aethriscus pani*. 4. Female from Ohrigstad, dorsal view showing their resemblance to bird droppings. 5. Anterior view showing the eye pattern. Credits: 4. Sharpview. 5. John Leroy.

Figure 6–11. *Aethriscus pani* female. 6–7. Epigyne. 8. Habitus line drawing, dorsal view. 9. Anterior view. 10. Posterior view. 11. Ventral view. Credits: 9–11. John Leroy; 6 & 8. After Lessert (1930).

Sternum heart-shaped (Fig. 2). Abdomen smooth and shiny covering almost half of the cephalothorax; twice as wide (19 mm) as it is long (8 mm); when viewed from above, displays a triangular shape (Figs 3 & 8); anterior edge of the abdomen scalloped, decorated with three tubercles, with 11 submarginal sigilla (Fig. 9); abdomen posteriorly concave with four slightly pronounced, rounded tubercles (Figs 8 & 10); dorsum with small round to oval sigilla forming round depressions around the border as well as four on the median area (Figs 3 & 10); ventrum with strikingly wrinkled sinuous grooves around spinnerets. Legs tawny with indistinct, blackish-tinted bands with layers of short setae (Fig. 5); tibiae and metatarsi are flattened and slightly unequal, with metatarsi shorter than tibiae, tibiae I and II with a slight curve (Figs 1 & 9). Epigyne concave at the base with two oval, transverse concavities and upward-pointed scape (Figs 6 & 7). Male unknown.

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo; South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Plot off Malmani Road, Cradle of Humankind, Krugersdorp (-26.03465, 27.69173). **Limpopo:** Krugerpos, Orighstad (-24.904, 30.549).

LIFESTYLE

The female specimen from Gauteng was collected at night from low bushes and grass near a bee hive with a sweepnet. She was kept in a terrarium for observation. She was active at night, spinning irregular lines of strong silk between twigs and grass. During the day she rested on the ground not on supplied vegetation. Unfortunately she died after a few days.

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